

CRIMINOLOGICAL AND LEGAL ASPECTS REGARDING THE CONDITIONS (CIRCUMSTANCES) AND CRIMINOGENIC PHENOMENA THAT INFLUENCE THE COMMITMENT OF CRIMES

Iurie LARII

ORCID: 0000-0003-4277-535X

Academy “Ștefan cel Mare” of MIA of the Republic of Moldova

Abstract. The article reflects the main ideas and concepts regarding the conditions that favor the commission of crimes, as well as the criminogenic phenomena that, although not considered criminal, actively fuel the crime and create a favorable environment for its existence and extension. The study of these aspects is quite relevant for criminological and legal sciences, as the most complete revision of the conditions (technical, organizational, psychological, etc.) that favor criminality, along with the causes that generate it, will streamline the process of preventing and combating the criminal phenomenon, which ensures a higher level of security for the population and society in general.

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Introduction

The problem of the causality of the criminal phenomenon is one of the most important in criminological science. The causes of crime have long been the subject of discussion for philosophers, jurists, and other thinkers. Even during the Renaissance, Thomas Morus, expounding his ideas in his famous work “Utopia”, rightly mentioned that when the causes of crime remain unchanged, the consequences of these causes will remain unchanged. Even the harshest sanctions are ineffective if the economic situation of the society is not improved or if other measures are not applied to eliminate the causes of the crime phenomenon¹.

Referring to the *causes of crime*, we find that these are social phenomena and processes that generate and maintain the existence of crime or cause it to increase or decrease.

The influence of the causes on the crime would be extremely difficult if the society lacks the phenomena and processes that favor the functioning of the causal mechanism. These

¹ *Криминология: учебник для юридических вузов.* Под общей ред. А.И. Долговой. Москва: Изд. группа НОРМА-ИНФРА-М, 1999. С. 11.

phenomena and processes are also called “conditions”, “circumstances” or “factors” that favor the commission of crimes.

Crime conditions (circumstances)

In criminology, by *conditions that favor the commission of crimes*, objective or subjective factors are taken into account that do not directly generate the crimes, but their existence can influence the appearance of the intention in a certain person to commit the crime. It is important to mention that the appreciation of some phenomena as causes, and others as conditions has a relative character, because in different situations one and the same phenomenon can appear both in the role of cause and condition.

The most common classification of conditions that favor the commission of crimes is their division into three main groups: 1) technical conditions; 2) organizational conditions; 3) psychological conditions.

The technical conditions refer to the particularities of place and time (night time, empty place, and crowded place), possession of the necessary equipment by the offender (weapon, transport, various tools for opening of premises), lack of an efficient security system, etc.

In general, these phenomena and processes (conditions) refer to different forms of manifestation of crime and can have their origin in various types of social relations, as well as in the mechanism of socio-state functioning. It is about the gaps in the technical-organizational sphere, as well as about some concrete fields - the guarding of the public or private patrimony, the lack of evidence or the weak evidence of the material goods, etc. Some conditions may arise as a result of the inefficient activity of various state bodies with specific responsibilities in the field of organizing the process of preventing and combating crime, such as the police, the prosecutor's office, the courts, etc. The control bodies and, first of all, the financial ones can also favor, through the imperfections in the organization of their activity, the appearance of some criminogenic conditions.

Psychological conditions (factors) are most often associated with the indifferent attitude of the population and the representatives of the law enforcement bodies towards the crimes committed (for example, failure to notify the competent authorities regarding crimes and other violations of the law, unfounded refusal to initiate criminal proceedings and to investigate the crime, etc.).

The assistance of accomplices offered to offenders may also be attributed to conditions which favor the commission of criminal offenses.

In some cases, these conditions may be present or may be absent, but the offense may not be committed. For example, the lack of a lock on the doors where material goods are kept is an

inherent condition that favors the commission of the crime of theft, but this may not be committed.

The conditions are easier to detect than the causes of the crime. In many cases they seem to be on the surface. Sometimes they are reflected in various branches of the economy or in the concrete spheres of human activity, for which reason it is simpler to prevent and eliminate them or to neutralize them.

The Code of Criminal Procedure of the Republic of Moldova (art. 216) stipulates the obligation of the criminal investigation bodies to establish the causes and conditions that favored the commission of the crime during the criminal investigation and trial of the case. Also, if these have been found, the criminal investigation body is obliged to notify the responsible person or the respective body regarding the need to take measures to remove these causes and conditions (paragraph (1), art. 217).

The removal of the causes and conditions of the crime should not be understood in its etymological sense, but as a recommendation from the authorized bodies with competence to carry out the criminal investigation, because it is not excluded that over a certain time the same criminal situation will be repeated.

As a rule, the removal of conditions that favor the commission of crimes does not require large financial investments. This measure contributes to the restoration of the violated order and is future-oriented, because any conscientious manager, for example, is concerned to protect his company (institution) against criminal attacks. Also, at the level of society, a situation of intolerance towards crimes is created, which has a special importance for the prevention of the criminal phenomenon.

The main criminogenic phenomena

The elucidation and characterization of the conditions (factors, circumstances) that facilitate the commission of crimes can be complemented by the analysis of *criminogenic phenomena* which, although not considered criminal, actively supplies crime and create a favorable environment for its existence and expansion. These include vagrancy, prostitution, alcoholism and drug addiction, which we will briefly refer to.

Vagrancy

Vagabonds are usually concentrated in urban areas, most of them in the largest cities in the country. Hundreds of homeless people are found in the Republic of Moldova every year.

In general, the criminogenic aspect of this phenomenon derives from the fact that people who practice vagrancy, not having a permanent place to live and work, are forced to acquire

means of subsistence through crime or other illegal methods. They often commit theft and are less likely to commit robbery or burglary. Some of the vagabonds are also being prosecuted by law enforcement bodies.

Vagabonds negatively influence those around them, especially minors, often involving them in begging, drunkenness, prostitution, including crime or other violations of the law. They often violate public order; and drunkenness, alcoholism, and beatings accompanied by swearing and hooliganism thrive in places of their concentration. Among the vagabonds there are many people who practice begging, suffer from various venereal diseases, tuberculosis or even some incurable and infectious diseases.

The vagabonds are characterized by the permanent change of their place of residence and the lack of a shelter. As a rule, they do not work or live in the same place for a longer period of time. However, if they have a job, they leave it as soon as possible, not intending to find another socially useful activity.

The main reason that generates the systematic practice of vagrancy is the unconscious aspiration of the individual to preserve his pseudo-freedom.

The elucidation of some aspects related to the childhood of vagabonds generates certain conclusions regarding their family environment, which, in turn, determines the formation of their personality and way of life. Thus, it is well known that one of the most important functions of the family is the involvement of children in the diversity of family relationships, being determined a certain place and role in it. In most cases, children who later became homeless did not benefit from parental affection and proper family treatment. Therefore, this fact is determined by the family structure, by the individual-psychological and moral peculiarities of the parents, but also by their way of life and behavior.

There are families in which the child loses or is abandoned by both parents at an early age, being left in the care of relatives or placed in an orphanage. Parents may motivate such a decision differently, but in fact their actions indicate a refusal to support and educate the child. Often, this category of children becomes vagabonds during their lifetime, and virtually they have no desire to ever return home to their parents. Alienation of children is the main cause of the maladaptive lifestyle, specific to a considerable number of homeless people. Usually, this alienation occurs as a result of the existence of unfavorable social conditions, which can be overcome by carrying out special measures of an educational-prophylactic nature.

Prostitution

Prostitution has existed since ancient times, in one form or another, open or latent, the number of prostitutes increasing especially in different periods of crisis (war, internal conflicts, economic and social recessions, etc.). At the same time, it is well known that organized crime

supports prostitution quite consistently; as such a form of sexual exploitation is an essential source of income. It is important to note that during the recent years, prostitution among men, including minors, has become more widespread. Today, some gay clubs are operating successfully, supported by various NGOs in the country or abroad, and media sources no longer face obstacles in the distribution of information on the provision of intimate services by young men. Information on the provision of sexual services by children, adolescents and adults is permanently posted on the Internet.

Historically, prostitution is considered to be the oldest “profession in the world”. Historical myths and attestations show that among ancient peoples, prostitution was not only tolerated, but even encouraged for various purposes². Thus, the men of ancient Greece believed that fine prostitution was necessary for pleasures’ satisfaction, and that there were several classes of prostitutes: haetera – luxury prostitutes, who offered physical pleasures and company on an intellectual level; peripatetica – street prostitutes; consecrated prostitutes, who activated in the temples. In Corinth, for example, the temple housed 1,000 well-known prostitutes who practiced sexual intercourse for a considerable price³.

From a legal point of view, the Contravention Code of the Republic of Moldova by art. 89 sanctions prostitution practicing, but when it comes to the categories of persons who obtain income as a result of prostitution of another or other persons then the respective actions will be included in the provisions of art. 220 of the Criminal Code, constituting the crime of pimping. Also, the norms of international law criminalize prostitution, especially the income from its practice.

According to official statistics, about 500 cases of prostitution are registered annually on the territory of the Republic of Moldova, of which about 75% are committed in Chişinău. More serious are cases of pimping, especially when they are committed by various organized criminal structures. If we analyze the statistical data in that department, we find that since 2013 this type of crime has had a constant dynamic increase, their maximum share being reached in 2016⁴.

When researching the issue of sexual exploitation through prostitution, it should be noted that it is essentially a complex of actions, carried out in a certain process, during which the perpetrators, intending to achieve the purpose of sexual exploitation, commit a series of criminal acts that present an increased social danger: kidnapping, illegal deprivation of liberty, torture,

² Michel Foucault. *Istoria sexualităţii*. Vol. 3. Preocuparea de sine. Tradus de Cătălina Vasile. Bucureşti: Editura Univers, 2004. P. 5-10.

³ D. Mihalache. *Traficul de persoane ca fenomen*. În: www.cercetarijuridice.ro/rrda/articole. Citat de: Ioan Gârbuleţ. *Traficul de persoane: practică judiciară comentată, legislaţie conexă, doctrină, decizii ale Curţii Constituţionale, recursuri în interesul legii, jurisprudenţă CEDO*. Bucureşti: Universul Juridic, 2010. P. 19.

⁴ Iu. Larii, O. Pohilă. *Infracţiunile de exploatare sexuală a femeilor şi copiilor: elemente de drept comparat, analiză criminologică şi măsuri de prevenire*. Chişinău: Departamentul Editorial-poligrafic al Academiei „Ştefan cel Mare”, 2021. P. 91.

inhuman or degrading treatment, intentional harm to bodily integrity or health, rape, violent sexual acts, sexual harassment, sexual intercourse with persons under the age of sixteen, perverse actions, etc. Obviously, the more difficult this process is, the more group activity is required to increase the effectiveness of criminal actions. In this sense, practice shows that the share of these crimes committed in the group ranges from 30% to 55%, and in some cases their share can reach 75%⁵.

In the context of the analysis of this phenomenon, it is important to mention the unfavorable situation that many young women from vulnerable families have, to whom access to certain valuables and various prestigious objects is practically limited. At the same time, due to the television, the press and social mobility, the degree of their information about these goods is quite high, and consequently there is the feeling of envy, but also that of injustice and neglect. These causes provoke some of them to practice prostitution, and ferocity and aggression often appear as a means of psychological compensation for enduring humiliation.

The OSCE Permanent Council has identified several criminogenic factors of sexual exploitation through prostitution, including: poverty, ineffectiveness of social structures, job shortages and limited employment opportunities, violence against women and children, gender discrimination, of race and ethnicity, corruption, the existence of unresolved conflicts and post-conflict situations, illegal migration and increased demand for sexual exploitation services, the presence of cheap labor, which is often illegally involved in the performance of various jobs, and is not socially and legally protected⁶.

Alcoholism and drug addiction

Both alcoholism and drug addiction are destructive phenomena for mankind. All these create chronic and enduring addictions that severely affect the lives and health of consumers, and ultimately suffer the whole of society.

Today, illicit drug trafficking has taken on a global character and has become a serious obstacle in the socio-economic, political and cultural development of modern society. It is unanimously acknowledged that the use of narcotics and their illegal circulation have a negative impact on human health, destroying their lives and families, compromising the harmonious development of the personality, generating crime and corruption⁷.

The influence of alcoholism and drug addiction on crime has long been known. Alcoholic and narcotic intoxication reduces or even stops behavioral self-control, changes the fundamental

⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 95-96.

⁶ Decision No. 557/Rev. 1 of 7 July 2005. *OSCE Action Plan to Combat Trafficking in Human Beings*. In: <http://www.osce.org/pc/15944?download=true>

⁷ Marian Nucu. *Prevenirea și combaterea infracțiunilor legate de circulația ilegală a substanțelor narcotice*. Teză de doctor în drept. Chișinău, 2016. P. 9.

mentality of the individual, develops aggression and impulsivity, causes jealousy and commits, based on it, multiple crimes, especially violent.

At the same time, alcoholism and narcotics lead to the degradation of the personality, the depreciation of social and moral values, the breakdown of family and work relationships, etc. As a rule, alcoholics and drug addicts do not work, and in order to obtain the necessary sources for the purchase of alcoholic beverages and drugs, they commit thefts, robberies, and burglaries, crimes of murder of material interest or other violent crimes with rather serious consequences. For example, some studies on violent crime⁸ show that their perpetrators have consumed alcohol or drugs to a large extent: 54% in the case of homicides, 41% in the case of rape and 36% in the case of robberies.

Therefore, in an environment where alcoholic beverages or drugs are systematically and abusively consumed, the likelihood of committing illicit acts, including criminal offenses, is substantially increased, which should be given greater attention in the process of taking measures to prevent such antisocial phenomena.

The crime created by drugs, through its social, economic, medical, cultural and political consequences, causes considerable damage not only to the interests of the state, but also to those of society, of many individuals, threatens the life and health of citizens, has a demoralizing influence on people's consciousness and behavior⁹.

At present, the production and consumption of drugs have experienced an extraordinary explosion, resulting from the profits obtained from illicit trafficking by organized criminal structures. Illicit drug trafficking is closely linked to other serious forms of crime, such as trafficking in migrants, trafficking in human beings, forgery of credit cards, and at the same time an important source of funding for particularly violent and destructive activities in which terrorist organizations and organized crime networks are involved. Criminals involved in illicit drug trafficking are taking an increasingly professional approach and adapting flexibly to the new geopolitical, legal, economic and technological conditions, using entrepreneurial structures and combining illegal business activities with legitimate commercial ones. At the same time, they are ready to act by any means to achieve their objectives, resorting to threats or acts of violence against persons and property, seeking to exert their influence in order to manipulate politicians, businessmen and public authorities, with the main purpose of maximizing profits and gaining power¹⁰.

⁸ Iu. Larii, R. Cojocaru, V. Ionașcu et al. *Criminalitatea violentă în Republica Moldova: tendințe generale, cauze și condiții*. Chișinău: Tipogr. Academiei „Ștefan cel Mare” a MAI, 2018. P. 32.

⁹ Gh. Alecu. *Mijloace juridice, strategii și programe destinate prevenirii criminalității create de traficul și consumul ilicit de droguri*. În: Revista de criminologie, de criminalistică și de penologie, nr. 4/2006. P. 129-130.

¹⁰ Iu. Larii, M. Nucu. *Pericolul și tendințele infracționalității legate de circulația ilegală a substanțelor narcotice*. În: Legea și viața, nr. 9 (285), 2015. P. 20.

Conclusions

In most cases, the presence of favorable conditions (circumstances) or criminogenic phenomena radically influences the commission of crimes, as well as criminality in general. For these reasons, the organization of the crime prevention process cannot be carried out efficiently without identifying and removing or neutralizing the conditions that favor the commission of criminal acts, as well as the main criminogenic phenomena that influence the continuous criminalization of society.

Bibliographical references:

1. *Криминология: учебник для юридических вузов*. Под общей ред. А.И. Долговой. Москва: Изд. группа НОРМА-ИНФРА·М, 1999.
2. Michel Foucault. *Istoria sexualității*. Vol. 3. Preocuparea de sine. Tradus de Cătălina Vasile. București: Editura Univers, 2004.
3. D. Mihalache. *Traficul de persoane ca fenomen*. În: www.cercetarijuridice.ro/rrda/articole. Citat de: Ioan Gârbuleț. *Traficul de persoane: practică judiciară comentată, legislație conexă, doctrină, decizii ale Curții Constituționale, recursuri în interesul legii, jurisprudență CEDO*. București: Universul Juridic, 2010.
4. Iu. Larii, O. Pohilă. *Infrațiunile de exploatare sexuală a femeilor și copiilor: elemente de drept comparat, analiză criminologică și măsuri de prevenire*. Chișinău: Departamentul Editorial-poligrafic al Academiei „Ștefan cel Mare”, 2021.
5. Decision No. 557/Rev. 1 of 7 July 2005. *OSCE Action Plan to Combat Trafficking in Human Beings*. In: <http://www.osce.org/pc/15944?download=true>
6. Marian Nucu. *Prevenirea și combaterea infracțiunilor legate de circulația ilegală a substanțelor narcotice*. Teză de doctor în drept. Chișinău, 2016.
7. Iu. Larii, R. Cojocaru, V. Ionașcu et al. *Criminalitatea violentă în Republica Moldova: tendințe generale, cauze și condiții*. Chișinău: Tipogr. Academiei „Ștefan cel Mare” a MAI, 2018.
8. Gh. Alecu. *Mijloace juridice, strategii și programe destinate prevenirii criminalității create de traficul și consumul ilicit de droguri*. În: Revista de criminologie, de criminalistică și de penologie, nr. 4/2006.
9. Iu. Larii, M. Nucu. *Pericolul și tendințele infracționalității legate de circulația ilegală a substanțelor narcotice*. În: Legea și viața, nr. 9 (285), 2015.

About the author

Iurie Larii, PhD, university professor, vice-rector for science of the Academy “Ștefan cel Mare” of MIA of the Republic of Moldova. E-mail: iulari72@gmail.com

Streszczenie. Artykuł odzwierciedla główne idee dotyczące warunków sprzyjających popełnianiu przestępstw, a także zjawisk kryminogennych, które choć nie są uznawane za przestępcze, aktywnie napędzają przestępczość i tworzą sprzyjające środowisko dla jej istnienia i rozprzestrzeniania się. Badanie tych aspektów jest bardzo istotne dla nauk kryminologicznych i prawnych, ponieważ jak najpełniejsza identyfikacja uwarunkowań (technicznych, organizacyjnych, psychologicznych itp.) przyczyniających się do przestępstwa, a także przyczyn, które go powodują, uprości proces zapobiegania i zwalczania zjawiska przestępczego, zapewniający wyższy poziom bezpieczeństwa ludności i całego społeczeństwa.

Zusammenfassung. Der Artikel spiegelt die Hauptgedanken in Bezug auf die Bedingungen, die der Begehung von Straftaten förderlich sind, sowie kriminogene Phänomene wider, die, obwohl sie nicht als kriminell gelten, die Kriminalität aktiv anheizen und ein günstiges Umfeld für ihre Existenz und Verbreitung schaffen. Die Untersuchung dieser Aspekte ist für die Kriminologie und Rechtswissenschaft von großer Bedeutung, da eine möglichst vollständige Identifizierung der Bedingungen (technischer, organisatorischer, psychologischer Art), die zur Kriminalität beitragen, sowie der Gründe, die dazu beitragen, vereinfacht wird der Prozess der Verhütung und Bekämpfung eines kriminellen Phänomens, der ein höheres Maß an Sicherheit für die Bevölkerung und die Gesellschaft insgesamt gewährleistet.

Резюме. В статье отражены основные идеи относительно условий, способствующих совершению преступлений, а также криминогенных явлений, которые, хотя и не считаются преступными, активно подпитывают преступность и создают благоприятную среду для ее существования и распространения. Изучение этих аспектов весьма актуально для криминологической и юридической науки, поскольку наиболее полное выявление условий (технических, организационных, психологических и т.д.), способствующих преступности, а также причин, порождающих ее, упростит процесс предотвращения и борьбы с преступным явлением, что обеспечивает более высокий уровень безопасности населения и общества в целом.